

PROPOSED DIGITIZED SELF-LEARNING MODULE IN SCIENCE FOR GRADE 7 LEARNERS

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Abstract. This study intended to propose a digitized self-learning module in Science 7 for the use of Grade 7 learners in Tarece Integrated School in District V-A San Carlos City Division, Pangasinan during the school year 2020-2021. Findings show that Grade 7 learners have low-level performance and have not mastered learning competencies in Science. Based on the evaluation of the proposed digitized self-learning module in Science 7 by the evaluators, the material is a highly acceptable learning resource material and should be used by Grade 7 teachers to enhance not mastered competencies of learners in Science.

Keywords. Digitized Self-Learning Module, Acceptability Level, Science, Performance Level

1 Introduction

Education has been the primary focus of different governments for centuries. In the Third World Setting, governments work hard to make sure that their universities, colleges, and basic education centers continue to provide a mechanism that can make its citizens intellectually capable, to contribute to the national economy. Education is the primary vehicle by which economically and socially marginalized adults and children can lift themselves out of poverty and obtain the means to participate fully in their communities (Victorino, 2011).

The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2019 shows the Philippines scored “significantly lower” than any other country that participated in Grade 4 Math and Science assessments. Filipino students lagged behind other countries in the TIMSS for Grade 4, the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study 2019 (TIMSS) revealed last December 8, 2019. The Philippines only scored 297 in mathematics and 249 in science, which are “significantly lower” than any other participating country. The country also scored the lowest among all 58 participating countries for both tests (Magsambol, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound and sudden impact on our lives. This pandemic paved the way for the implementation of modular distance learning as an urgent response to ensure the continuity of education. Modular Distance Learning uses Self-Learning Modules based on the most essential learning competencies provided by the Department of Education.

The self-learning module is an individualized method of learning. Face-to-face teaching is not allowed during the pandemic, and distance mode of education is becoming popular. With the advent of information and technology for communication, the other modes of instruction are replaced. The learner is getting accustomed more and more to the non-formal mode of education thereby shifting the preference to self-learning modules (A.H. Sequeira, 2012).

Self-learning modules are delivered in printed forms to communities without access to the internet or electricity and to those students who cannot afford load expenses. Using self-learning modules in printed form may have advantages during this pandemic in the educational process but there are also some challenges experienced by teachers, especially in teaching Science as one of the core subjects. Observations in the students using printed modular learning include the low level of performance because of limited instruction in printed modular learning materials. The Department of Education also announced that self-learning modules can also be accessed online or offline. Offline learning (or viewing) of e-learning courses is simply the ability to open or run a course without being connected to the Internet.

Department of Education Secretary, Leonor M. Briones pointed out in the Department of Education Information and Communication Technology (DepEd ICT) National Summit that teachers are urged to devise various teaching methods that instill creativity and critical thinking among learners through Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The

challenge to devise materials that can help enhance and assist learners' performances is gravely dependent on teachers. Educators are urged to foster creativity by coming up with various materials that (ICT)-based on (Montemayor, 2018).

With this current situation in education, the researcher encountered difficulties in the delivery of instruction through distance learning materials. Learners also encounter difficulties in answering their modules since there is limited interaction with the teacher brought about by the pandemic. During the parents' meeting, most of the complaints the teachers received were the struggles of parents in assisting and guiding the learners at home since they also had limited knowledge about the lesson. Learners with parents working were also struggling to learn independently.

To ensure the transfer of learning and delivery of quality instruction, the researcher to conduct this study and propose a digitized self-learning module as another alternative instructional material. Responding to the current situation of teaching and learning, this study attempted to propose a possible measure to help the learners enhance their scientific literacy using self-learning modules even without the teacher's assistance. For this reason, this study aimed to propose and develop digitized self-learning modules in Science for those learners with household technologies (television, desktop computer, laptop, and smartphone).

2 Review of Related Literature

The researcher presented various studies relevant to the present study that provided inputs to the present study. They provided significant insights that will help the researcher in the development of the Proposed Digitized Self-Learning Module in Science for Grade 7 learners.

The above-mentioned studies by Bukoye (2021), Mejia (2019), Forelo (2019), Resngit (2016), and Yang et al. (2014) recommend the use of computer-assisted instructional materials could help develop and enhance learners' performance. This material could be of great help to teachers in delivering quality and effective instruction. Furthermore, Basilan (2018) reiterated that effective and adequate usage of instructional materials depends on teachers. Likewise, Onasanya and Omoewo (2016) recommend the improvement of instructional materials in Physics. It is the teachers' responsibility to use appropriate instructional materials for the attainment of learning objectives and for effective, and better transfer of learning.

On the other hand, Mendiguarin (2017) stated in his study that the use of digitized instructional materials is a helpful tool for learners to be actively engaged in the teaching-learning process. The use of digitized instructional materials as compared to other forms of instructional material is more engaging and lasting. The present study is different from the other studies since it has different subjects, locale, and research design. On the other hand, the present study has similarities with the study of Nyarko, et al. (2020) which sought to explore distance education students' readiness to use digital learning materials. It has also similarities to the proposed project of Jimenez (2021), In his paper he introduces the proposal entitled Project NEW-NORMAL which provide substantial support in the learning modalities of students and cater basic needs of teacher and students for the teaching and learning process.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study made use of the descriptive-developmental method of research. It is descriptive because the researcher described and analyzed the results of the quarterly summative test of the Grade 7 learners in Science during the first and second quarters of the school year 2020-2021.

Likewise, this study employed the developmental method of research because an output was developed by the researcher which is the digitized self-learning module in Grade 7 Science that was based on the analysis of quarterly summative test results. The not mastered learning competencies for the first and second quarters were the basis for the development of the digitized self-learning module.

3.2 Sources of Data

This study made use of the Summative test results of 71 Grade 7 learners during the first and second quarters of the school year 2020-2021. Two sections of Grade 7 learners in Tarece Integrated School are the sources of data. The frequency distribution of Evaluators (Grade 7 Science Teachers in San Carlos City Division District V-A, Science Master Teacher, Education Program Supervisor in Science and Learning Resource Development, and Management System Supervisor).

The researcher analyzed the results of the first and second-quarter summative test results of Grade 7 learners in Science. On the other hand, the proposed digitized self-learning module in Science for Grade 7 learners was evaluated by Science 7 Teachers in District V-A, Science Master Teacher, Education Program Supervisor in Science, and Learning Resource Management and Development System supervisor to determine the level of acceptability of the said material as to its content, instructional design, and technical quality.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To determine the not mastered competencies of Grade 7 learners in Science, an item analysis of the quarterly summative test during the first and second quarters was conducted. The results of the item analysis were described in terms of the percentage of correct response (PCR).

To determine the level of acceptability of the proposed digitized self-learning module in Science 7, a 4-point Likert scale was used to interpret the results of the evaluation based on a given set of criteria such as content instructional quality and technical quality.

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Level of Performance and Not Mastered Competencies of Grade 7 Learners in Science-Based on the Item Analysis of the First and Second Quarterly Summative Test Results of the School Year 2020-2021

Table 2 presents the descriptive equivalent of the level of performance of 71 Grade 7 learners based on the analysis of first and second-quarter summative test results during the school year 2020-2021. Out of 71 learners in Grade 7, 10 learners obtained a very low level of performance which means the results of their scores range from 1-2. 19 learners out of 71 got a low level of performance with scores ranging from 26-50. 9 learners out of 71 got a very high level of performance which means their first and second quarter summative test result scores range from 76-100. Out of 71 learners, 33 of them attained a moderately high level of performance and obtained scores ranging from 51-75.

Table 1. Level of Performance of Grade 7 Learners in Science Based on the Analysis of First and Second Quarter Summative Tests During the School Year 2020-2021
N-71

Scale	Frequency of Scores	Descriptive Equivalent
76-100	9	Very High
51-75	33	Moderately High
26-50	19	Low
1-25	10	Very Low

Table 2 presents the findings that out of 14 learning competencies for the first and second quarter in Science 7 during the school year 2020-2021, the highlighted part is 2 learning competencies wherein learners obtained not mastered a level of performance. This learning competency recognizes that substances are classified into elements and compounds (58%) from the first quarter and differentiates plant and animal cells according to the presence or absence of certain organelles (59%) for the second quarter. This not-mastered competency is the basis for the development of the proposed digitized self-learning module.

The same table also shows that there are 7 learning competencies wherein learners obtained nearly mastered competencies. For the first quarter, these are distinguished mixtures from substances based on a set of properties (65%) and express concentrations of solutions quantitatively by preparing different concentrations of mixtures according to uses and availability of materials (64%). For second-quarter summative test results, competencies obtained nearly mastery are focus specimens using the compound microscope (73%), explain why the cell is considered the basic structural and functional unit of all organisms (67%), differentiate asexual from sexual reproduction (65%), describe the different ecological relationships found in an ecosystem (65%) and predict the changes in abiotic factors on the ecosystem (65%).

Table 2 also shows that there are 5 mastered learning competencies. For the first quarter, these describe the components of scientific investigation (75%) and investigate properties of unsaturated or saturated solutions (75%). For the second quarter mastered competencies and identified parts of the microscope and their functions (75%), described the different levels of biological organization from cell to biosphere (76%), and differentiated biotic from abiotic components of an ecosystem.

Table 2. Level of Performance of Grade 7 Learners in Science Based on the Analysis of First and Second Quarter Summative Tests During the School Year 2020-2021
N-71

Science 7 First Quarter Learning Competencies	Percentage of Correct Response	Descriptive Equivalent
Describe the components of a scientific investigation (S7MT-Ia-1)	75%	Mastered
Recognize that substances are classified into elements and compounds (S7MT-Ig-h-5)	58%	Not Mastered
Distinguish mixtures from substances based on a set of properties (S7MT-Ie-f-4)	65%	Nearly Mastered
Investigate properties of unsaturated or saturated solutions (S7MT-Ic-2)	75%	Mastered
Express concentrations of solutions quantitatively by preparing different concentrations of mixtures according to uses and availability of materials (S7MT-Id-3)	64%	Nearly Mastered
Average PCR for First Quarter	67.4 %	Nearly Mastered
Science 7 Second Quarter Learning Competencies	Percentage of Correct Response	Descriptive Equivalent
Identify parts of the microscope and their functions (S7LT-IIa-1)	75%	Mastered
Focus specimens using the compound microscope (S7LT-Iib-2)	73%	Nearly Mastered
Describe the different levels of biological organization from cell to biosphere (S7LT-Iic-3)	76%	Mastered
Differentiate plant and animal cells according to presence or absence of certain organelles (S7LT-Iic-3)	59%	Not Mastered
Explain why the cell is considered the basic structural and functional unit of all organisms (S7LT-Iie-5)	67%	Nearly Mastered
Differentiate asexual from sexual reproduction in terms of: 1 Number of individuals involved; 2 Similarities of offspring to parents (S7LT-Iig-7)	65 %	Nearly Mastered
Differentiate biotic from abiotic components of an ecosystem (S7LT-Iih-9)	76%	Mastered
Describe the different ecological relationships found in an ecosystem(S7LT-Iih-10)	61%	Nearly Mastered
Predict the effect of changes in abiotic factors on the ecosystem (S7LT-Iij-12)	65%	Nearly Mastered
Average PCR for Second Quarter	68.55 %	Nearly Mastered
Over-All Weighted Mean	67.98%	Nearly Mastered

4.2 Evaluation of Grade 7 Teachers of District V-A

the findings of Grade 7 Science teachers in District V-A who were asked to evaluate the level of acceptability of the proposed digitized self-learning module in Science 7 based on a set of criteria such as content quality consistent with topics found in the DepEd Most Essential Learning Competencies in Science for Grade 7 learners. As to the content quality, it could be gleaned from the same table that the proposed digitized self-learning module is "highly acceptable" as evidenced by the overall average weighted mean of 3.42.

As to the instructional quality, the Grade 7 teacher-evaluator rated the proposed digitized self-learning module as "highly acceptable" gaining an overall average weighted mean of 3.71. Therefore, the digitized self-learning module is appropriate for use as instructional material in Science for Grade 7 learners. Looking intently at Table 4A, it could be noted that content quality and instructional quality are rated "highly acceptable" as shown by the overall computed average weighted means of 3.42 and 3.71 for each criterion.

4.3 Evaluation of Science Master Teacher and Education Program Supervisor

Table 4B reveals the results of the evaluation conducted by the Master Teacher and Education Program Supervisor on the proposed digitized self-learning module in Science 7. As to the content quality and instructional quality, the proposed digitized self-learning module was rated as "highly acceptable" by the Master Teacher and Education Program Supervisor with an average rating of 3.9 and 3.6 respectively in terms of content quality. Also for instructional quality, the master teacher and education program supervisor rated the digitized self-learning module as "highly accepted" with an average rating of 3.7 and 3.7. This implies that utilizing digitized self-learning modules will not only improve learning methods to enhance learning interest for the students, but also afford for learning anywhere, at any place, and at any time. The application of computer technology has great potential to increase students' motivation and improve the quality of teachers' teaching and students' learning.

4.4 Evaluation of Learning Resource Management and Development System Supervisor

The evaluation made by the Learning Resource Management and Development System supervisor in terms of its technical design was given a rate of 3.66 as "highly acceptable". Based on the results, it could be deduced that the proposed digitized self-learning module in Science 7 could still be improved on certain criteria so that the intention of addressing the learning difficulties of the learners in Science 7 could be achieved. As stated in the study by Mendiguarin (2017), he found out that digitized instructional materials allow learners to be actively engaged in the learning process. Visual materials have been used in every field and technological devices especially computers, have affected the learners. As a result, instructional materials that are supported by sounds, images, and animations are observed to become more lasting, enjoyable, and effective.

4.5 Summary of Evaluation Results of the Proposed Digitized Self-Learning Module in Science 7 by Criterion

It could be noted that along the three criteria such as content quality, instructional quality, and technical design the Education Program Supervisor in Science, Master Teacher, Grade 7 Science Teachers in District V-A, and Division Learning Resource Management and Development System Supervisor rated the proposed digitized self-learning modules as "highly acceptable" based on the computed over-all average weighted mean of 3.64 for the content quality, while along the other criteria, the four groups of respondent rated the proposed digitized self-learning module in Science 7 as "highly acceptable" as indicated by the overall average weighted mean of 3.70 for the criteria of instructional quality. On the other hand, the results of the evaluation of the proposed digitized self-learning module in Science as to its technical design made by the Learning Resource Management and Development System Supervisor rated 3.67 and manifest as "highly acceptable" and appropriate to use for the learners in the teaching-learning process.

Table 3. Summary of Evaluation Results of the Proposed Digitized Self-Learning Module in Science 7 by Criterion

Criteria	Evaluators				OAWM	DE
	Grade 7 Science Teachers	Science Master Teacher	Science Education Program Supervisor in	LDRDMS Supervisor		
	N-21	N-1	N-1	N-1		
Content Quality	3.42	3.9	3.6		3.64	HA
Instructional Quality	3.71	3.7	3.7		3.70	HA
Technical Quality				3.67	3.67	HA
GENERAL OVER-ALL AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN					3.67	HA

Based on the results of the evaluation of the proposed digitized self-learning module in Science 7. The indicators content quality, instructional quality, and technical quality were rated 3.64, 3.70, and 3.67 respectively with a general overall average weighted mean of 3.67 which could be described as “highly acceptable”.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The performance level of Science 7 learners is moderately high based on the results of the first and second-quarter summative tests. The not mastered learning competencies in Science 7 based on the item analysis of the first and second quarter summative test are 1. Recognize that substances are classified into elements and compounds (58%) and Differentiate plant and animal cells according to the presence or absence of certain organelles (59%). The proposed digitized self-learning module is for use of Grade 7 learners in Science to enhance not mastered learning competencies. The proposed digitized self-learning module in Science 7 was rated 3.64 for content quality, 3.70 for instructional quality by Grade 7 Science teachers in District V-A, Master Teacher, and Education Program Supervisor, and rated 3.67 for technical quality by the Learning Resource Development and Management System supervisor resulted to a general over-all weighted mean of 3.67 which could be described as “highly acceptable”.

The learner's level of performance can be evaluated. The learners not mastered competencies can be addressed. The proposed digitized self-learning module could be developed to be used for enhancing not mastered competencies of learners. The proposed digitized self-learning modules in Science 7 could pass the level of acceptability upon evaluation of Grade 7 Science teachers in District V-A, Master Teachers, Science Education Program Supervisors, and Learning Resource Development and Management supervisor

Teachers should enhance the learners' level of performance in Science. Teachers should address not mastered competencies of learners in Science. The proposed digitized self-learning module in Science 7 should be recommended for use by other Grade 7 Science teachers. Teachers should develop other forms of intervention materials for successful teaching-learning outcomes. Similar studies should be conducted in Science 7 focusing on other factors not included in this study such as other topics.

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